

A W A R E

Aquaponics from Wastewater Reclamation

Cycle I results – May 2025

www.aware-eu.eu

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AWARE is a consortium of 20 different entities (academia, industry, institutional bodies and international organisations) from 7 Members States of the EU and one extra-European country.

12 Research centers

5 SMEs

1 non-profit association

1 Government authority

1 International organisation

Introduction

AWARE (Aquaponics from **WA**stewater **RE**clamation) is a Horizon Europe-funded project launched on November 1, 2022, pioneering sustainable **fish farming** and urban food production by integrating an **aquaponic farm** into a **wastewater treatment plant**, to make use of **reclaimed water**.

The project is establishing a novel value chain for reclaimed water aquaponics food products by:

- Building **the first European** aquaponic demo-scale farm (TRL 6) that uses reclaimed water to produce fish and vegetables fit for human consumption
- Creating a **new business model** for the economic exploitation of said value chain by lakeside, riverside, and urban communities, including product traceability
- Informing regulations with scientific findings while **overcoming policy barriers** for upscaling and commercializing this novel solution

A Milestone: Two Years of Progress

28 months+

This booklet marks the completion of **AWARE**'s first cycle, and provides an at-glance update on achievements, ongoing developments, and next steps. Over the past 28 months, AWARE built the first reclaimed water aquaponics pilot in Castellana Grotte (Italy), tested advanced water treatment processes, and initiated policy discussions at national and EU levels. As the project moves forward, the focus shifts towards scaling the system, refining technology, and measuring impact to support future adoption of reclaimed water aquaponics across Europe.

***Reclaimed water** is wastewater that has been treated and purified to a level where it can be reused for specific non-potable purposes. In AWARE, it undergoes 4 treatment steps (primary, secondary, tertiary and, you guessed it, quaternary).*

Aerial view of the pilot site, in the wastewater treatment plant of Castellana Grotte (IT)

Pilot description

The Site

The pilot is located within the municipal wastewater treatment plant of Castellana Grotte – Bari, Italy (Coordinates: 40°53'21"N; 17°10'56"0" E)

The surface area of the pilot site, including empty space between buildings, is approximately 1.700 m² and consists of:

- Equilibration ponds holding water after tertiary treatment
- Solar panels
- Building housing ozonation system and vacuum UV
- External biofilters
- The geodesic dome, housing a small-scale aquaponic system (designed for experimental testing and optimization of reclaimed water use in a controlled environment)
- The greenhouse, housing a mid-scale aquaponic system (aimed at scaling up production and validating the commercial viability of aquaponics under near-operational conditions)

1. Equilibration tank 1
2. Equilibration tank 2
3. Solar panels
4. Ozonation and Vacuum-UV
5. External biofilter
6. Greenhouse with mid-scale aquaponic system
7. Geodesic dome with three small-scale aquaponic systems

Equilibration ponds with collection point of tertiary-treated wastewater

Solar panels next to the equilibration ponds

Quaternary treatment

How does it work?

Ozonation unit

VuV and MITO₃X®

Reservoir of water before treatment of the MITO₃X® (in the laboratory room)

Ozonation and Vacuum UV

Key properties:

- Max. water volume treated: 10 m³/h
- Energy requirement (estimate): 1.5 – 5 KWh/m³
- Capital cost requirement (estimate):
 - Ozone + VUV (including PLC and Sensors) = 100,000 €
 - Reactive storage / biofilter = 100,000 €

Inlet

Outlet

Outlet

Outlet

Biofilters

Quaternary treatment consists of a) **ozonation** (O₃) enhanced by **advanced mixing** (MiTO₃X®); b) **vacuum ultraviolet** (VUV) irradiation; c) **biofiltration** and reactive storage. Quaternary treatment removes trace pollutants, including heavy metals, contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), viruses, bacterial microbiota, and parasites. The system **reduces contamination** below the detection limit for all regulated metals except arsenic, thereby meeting the stringent quality standards required for water reuse in sensitive applications such as aquaponics.

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs)

Enhanced Ozonation

The ozonation process is implemented through the MITO₃X[®] unit, a proprietary technology developed by one of our partners, AQUASOIL SRL. This unit is capable of dosing and mixing gaseous and liquid reagents in a single treatment step, thus improving the efficiency of ozonation. The integrated vacuum UV further enhances the oxidation process. The system is designed for the removal of bacteria, viruses, and micropollutants in reclaimed urban wastewater for aquaponic reuse.

- **Target contaminants:**

- Bacteria (e.g., E. coli, total coliforms, fecal enterococci)

- Viruses (e.g., Norovirus, Hepatitis A/E, crAssPhage)

- Antibiotic resistance genes (e.g., int11, sul1, tetX)

- Organic micropollutants (e.g., pharmaceuticals, pesticides)

- Metals and parasites

- **Reagents used:**

- Ozone (O₃)

- Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) - 17.5mg/L

- **Operating conditions:**

- Flow rate: 6 m³/h

- O₃ dosage range tested: 2–6 mg/L

- Contact time: < 10 seconds (minimizing bromate formation)

- O₃ residual: Ranged from 0.4 to 2.09 mg/L

- Conductivity and nitrogen species remained within safe limits for aquaculture

Vacuum UV (VUV)

The VUV photoreactor uses lamps to generate hydroxyl radicals and directly photolyze contaminants. It operates in series with the ozonation unit to further oxidize refractory organic compounds and microbial DNA.

- **Target pollutants:**

Organic micropollutants (e.g., diclofenac)

Viruses and microbial DNA

Antibiotic resistance genes

- **Operating Conditions:**

Irradiation wavelengths: 185 nm and 254 nm

Water residence time: Not explicitly reported, but part of continuous flow after ozonation

Biofilters

Biofiltration uses natural microbes to remove residual contaminants through biological activity.

- **Biofilter Volume:**

24 m³ (7 m x 3.2 m x 1.1 m) extended design for the pilot plant, providing 24-hour empty bed contact time at 1 m³/h flow

- **Media bed:** a combination of:

- 3.18 mc activated carbon

- 6.62 mc expand clay

- 4.41 mc lava rock

Aquaponic Farm

1

Geodesic dome with small-scale aquaponic systems

designed for experimental testing and optimization of reclaimed water use in a controlled environment

Recirculating Aquaculture System

AWARE operates **three** parallel **Recirculation Aquaculture Systems (RAS)** lines, where fishes and vegetables are grown.

RAS 1 and RAS 2 (Reclaimed water lines):

Experimental lines running on reclaimed water, testing for optimal reclaimed water conditions.

RAS 3 (Freshwater control line):

Control running on freshwater to compare performance and quality against reclaimed water systems.

1. Fish tank
2. Mechanical filter
3. Sump tank
4. Media bed
5. Cultivation bed

Our pilot farm is producing Tilapia and Iceberg lettuce. The system has been designed after the commercial model “Blue Garden” from our project partner Green in Blue.

Configuration of the small-scale RAS

- Volume of water in the system: 2,750L x line
- Max. potential fish capacity (e.g., Tilapia): 50 adults x line x cycle
- Max. potential plants capacity (e.g., Lettuce): 164
- Expected fish productivity in standard conditions: 36 Kg/year
- Expected plant productivity in standard conditions: 300 Kg/year
- Expected sludge production in standard conditions: 5 liters/week/line
- Energy requirement (estimate): 150W times 24 hours of operation per day, heaters excluded
- Work requirement (estimate): 4h/week/line, including planting and harvesting
- Capital cost requirement (estimate): 18,500€/line (coordination, materials + installation)

2

Greenhouse with mid-scale RAS plant

aimed at scaling up production and validating the commercial viability of aquaponics under near-operational conditions)

Configuration of the mid-scale RAS

- Volume of water in the system: 12,000 L
- Max. fish capacity (e.g., Tilapia): 300
- Max. plants capacity (e.g. Lettuce): 500
- Expected fish productivity in standard conditions: 200 Kg/year
- Expected plant productivity in standard conditions: 900 Kg/year
- Expected sludge production in standard conditions: 30 litres/week/line
- Energy requirement (estimate): 750W times 24 hours of operation per day, heaters excluded
- Work requirement (estimate): 20h/week, including planting and harvesting
- Capital cost requirement (estimate): 98,200€/line (coordination, materials + installation)

IoT component/ Sensor installed	Function
Senect Aquaculture Pro	A central monitoring control system that monitors physical water quality parameters, manages and automates processes in aquaculture, like oxygen control, feeding, and alarms.
Senect pH XR1 Sonde	Measures the pH value of water precisely, important for monitoring water quality in fish tanks or ponds.
Senect ORP XT1 Sonde	Measures the oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) of water, which indicates how clean or oxidizing the water is.
Senect O2S Sensor	Measures the dissolved oxygen concentration in water to ensure optimal oxygen levels for fish health and system balance.

*Greenhouse housing the mid-scale RAS
(by GreeninBlue, from May 2025)*

Cycle I results

Start Date (Fish Introduction): August 12, 2024

End Date (Fish Harvest): December 2, 2024

Environmental Conditions:

- Average Water Temperature: 22.3°C
- Nutrient Supplementation:

At the beginning of the cycle, a complete starting salt supplement was added to each RAS to support optimal plant growth. The formulation included: 0.28 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 0.6 mM KNO_3 , 0.02 mM MgSO_4 , 0.02 mM NH_4NO_3 , 0.02 mM KH_2PO_4 , 2 μM Fe-EDTA, 0.9 μM H_3BO_3 , 7.5 nM CuSO_4 , 160 nM MnCl_2 , 15.4 nM ZnSO_4 , 2.2 nM $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_2^ \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. To prevent micronutrient deficiencies, especially iron, an additional 0.5 g Fe-EDTA solution per RAS was added biweekly.*

Fish Feeding Regimen:

- Feed Type: Aller Performa
- Feeding Frequency: Three times per day
- Total Feed Administered: 12 kg per tank over the entire cycle
- Fish Dietary Supplementation: None

Throughout Cycle I, continuous remote and on-site monitoring highlighted critical areas for improving the biofiltration system. In response, key upgrades were implemented in early March to enhance performance and reliability. These included the installation of more powerful pumps, redesigned tank inlets for better solid waste removal, upgraded piping, and new flow meters for real-time monitoring. Additionally, the design for a large-scale, next-generation biofilter has been finalized, with prefabrication completed and installation planned for May. These enhancements are making the biofilters more efficient, easier to maintain, and fully scalable - laying the foundation for a more robust and sustainable aquaponic system.

Water quality

Contaminant	Before Quaternary (F)				After Quaternary (I)	In aquaponic system (latest timepoint = cycle 1 M1)		
	77 (Including PFOA, PFBS, PFBA, PFHxA)					RAS 1 (reclaimed water)	RAS 2 (reclaimed water)	RAS 3 (tap water)
Organic contaminants	77 (Including PFOA, PFBS, PFBA, PFHxA)				1 (No PFAS detected)	M1: 16 (PFBS detected)	M1: 13	M1: 14
Pathogen Microbes	Mesophilic bacteria (CFU/100mL)	>500			Not conclusive	Not conclusive	Not conclusive	Not conclusive
	Total coliform (MNP/100 mL)	>2420						
	<i>E. coli</i> (MNP/100 mL)	< DL						
	Fecal enterococci (MNP/100 mL)	>2420						
Viruses (CrASS Phage, PMMoV, SaV, NoV-GI, GII, HEV, HAV)	CrAss Phage= 8.57E02 gc/L PMMoV= 2.55E05 gc/L Infective particles 30%				CrAss Phage= ND PMMoV= 1.86E04 gc/L Infective particles= 0%	< LoQ	< LoQ	< LoQ
Microplastics	2432 ± 55 particles/5 L				876 ± 28 particles/5 L	4950 ± 55 particles/5 L	4142 ± 55 particles/5 L	2184 ± 55 particles/5 L
Metals	<DL (PNEC, EPA)				<DL (PNEC, EPA)	<DL (PNEC, EPA)	<DL (PNEC, EPA)	<DL (PNEC, EPA)
Parasite reads (18S rRNA gene)	298-2443				102-147	100	99	2
16S rRNA	6.19 16S rRNA Log gc/mL				5.34 16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA	6.65 16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA	5.98 16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA	5.89 16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA
16S rRNA rocks biofilter top and bottom						5.16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA	5.16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA	5.16S rRNA Log gc/ngDNA

Microbial and chemical hazards

Analysis of **Tilapias** produced in the RASs

Organic contaminants	Concentration in fish tissue	Reference value ¹ (standard fish)
Sum of dioxins	<0.343	3.5 pg/g wet weight
Sum of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs	<0.549	6.5 pg/g wet weight
Sum of non dioxin-like PCBs	<2.00	75 ng/g wet weight
Sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS	0.135	2.0 µg/kg

Foodborne pathogens	Concentration in fish tissue	Reference value ² (standard fish)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NOT DETECTED	Ready-to-eat foods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limit of 100 CFU/g for products placed on the market during their shelf-life • absence in 25g, before the food has left the immediate control of the food business operator, who has produced it
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	NOT DETECTED	Absence in 25g (standard for most regulated foods to ensure consumer safety)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NOT DETECTED	Most stringent restriction is 1-10 CFU/g for shelled and shucked cooked crustaceans and molluscan shellfish

¹ Commission Regulation (EU) No 2023/915 of 25 April 2023 on maximum levels for certain contaminants in food, repealing Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006

² Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs.

Other pathogens	Concentration in fish tissue	Reference value ³ (standard fish)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	NOT DETECTED	Intestinal enterococci- Limit: 0/100ml
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> (non-regulated)	NOT DETECTED	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (non-regulated)	NOT DETECTED	-

Viruses (non-regulated)	Concentration in fish tissue	Reference value (standard fish)
Norovirus (Genogroups I and II)	NOT DETECTED	-
Hepatitis (HAV, HEV)	NOT DETECTED	-
Sapovirus	Muscle: 3.98E+04 GC/g	-
	Skin: <LoQ (3.11E+03 GC/g)	-
Peper mild mottle virus (PMMoV)	Muscle: 1.05E+05 GC/g	-
	Skin: 4.66E+03 GC/g	-

Foodborne pathogens and chemical contaminants were either undetectable or significantly below regulatory thresholds.

While trace amounts non-regulated viruses were detected, they pose no established health risk, as they fall outside current safety frameworks.

The data demonstrates that tilapia raised in reclaimed water, using the AWARE system, **meets safety standards for human consumption.**

³ Directive (EU) 2020/2184 on the quality of water intended for human consumption

Analysis of **Lettuces** produced in the RASs

Foodborne pathogens	Concentration in lettuces	Reference value ² (standard lettuces)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NOT DETECTED	Ready-to-eat foods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limit of 100 CFU/g for products placed on the market during their shelf-life • absence in 25g, before the food has left the immediate control of the food business operator, who has produced it
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	NOT DETECTED	Pre-cut fruit and vegetables (ready-to-eat): absence in 25 g
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NOT DETECTED	Pre-cut fruit and vegetables (ready-to-eat): limits 100-1000 CFU/g
Other pathogens³		
<i>Enterococcus</i>	Leaves: 4100 CFU/g	Intestinal enterococci-Limit: 0/100mL
	Roots: 125 CFU/g	
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> (non-regulated)	NOT DETECTED	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (non-regulated)	NOT DETECTED	-

² Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs.

³ Directive (EU) 2020/2184 on the quality of water intended for human consumption

Viruses (non-regulated)	Concentration in lettuces	Reference value (standard lettuces)
Norovirus (Genogroups I and II)	Leaves: NoV GII <LoQ (1.22E+03)	-
	Roots: NOT DETECTED	
Hepatitis (HAV, HEV)	Leaves: NOT DETECTED	-
	Roots: NOT DETECTED	
Sapovirus	Leaves: <LoQ (3.72E+03 GC/g)	-
	Roots: <LoQ (3.50E+02 GC/g)	
Peper mild mottle virus (PMMoV)	Leaves: 7.0E+03 GC/g	-
	Roots: <LoQ (3.13E+02 GC/g)	

The results support the microbiological safety and viability of aquaponic-grown lettuce under current operating conditions. The detection of Enterococcus is likely due to contamination during cultivation and post-handling.

The data indicate that lettuces grown using reclaimed water in **AWARE** aquaponic systems meet food safety standards, with no detected presence of key bacterial pathogens

Yields of fish and veggies quality

	Start of cycle			End of cycle		
	Ras 1	Ras 2	Ras 3 (control)	Ras 1	Ras 2	Ras 3 (control)
N° fishes	157	157	157	70	70	60
N° plants (Refers to an experiment > 4 weeks, started 2 weeks after the fish start)	10	10	10	10	10	10
Average fish size (cm)	8.28	8.28	8.28	15.29	17.28	15.80
Average fish weight (g)	10.66	10.66	10.66	65.01	95.54	73.68
Average plant biomass (g)	2.2	2.1	2.2	62	57	65

Tilapia grew from ~10 g to 65–95 g per fish in one cycle, reaching up to 17 cm in length. Lettuce increased from ~2 g to 57–65 g per head, with no differences between reclaimed-water and freshwater systems. Some nutrient supplementation (iron and salts) was needed, but once applied, production was steady. Overall, the pilot achieved tenfold fish growth and a 30-fold increase in lettuce biomass, showing that reclaimed water can sustain safe and efficient aquaponic yields.

Looking ahead

Cycle I of **AWARE** marks a significant milestone in proving the feasibility and safety of reclaimed water aquaponics.

With results coming in from our small scale pilot demonstrated that the fish and vegetables produced in the system can be used for human consumption, we are now setting up a larger scale aquaponic farm capable of supporting production throughout 2025 and 2026.

The fish produced is going to be used in a feeding trial with volunteers at the University of Ulster, with the aim of studying the nutritional effects and the acceptability of reclaimed-water Tilapia.

In the meantime, we continue to work with the authorities to create the regulatory framework necessary to allow reclaimed water to be used in aquaculture

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